

A The details of Example 1

To illustrate the proposed verification approach, we analyze the canonical 3-gate circuit shown in Fig. 1a. This circuit implements a CNOT operation between working qubits q_0 and q_1 mediated by an ancilla q_a . The system comprises working qubits $W = \{q_0, q_1\}$ and an ancilla $A = \{q_a\}$. The ancilla is initialized in $|0\rangle_a$ and is expected to return to $|0\rangle_a$.

State Vector Evolution First, we verify the clean ancilla safety by tracing the evolution of computational basis states. Let the input state be $|x, y\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} |0\rangle_a$, where $x, y \in \{0, 1\}$. The evolution of the global state $|\psi\rangle$ proceeds as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} |\psi_0\rangle &= |x\rangle_{q_0} |y\rangle_{q_1} |0\rangle_{q_a} \\ &\xrightarrow{\text{CNOT}(q_0, q_a)} |x\rangle_{q_0} |y\rangle_{q_1} |x\rangle_{q_a} \\ &\xrightarrow{\text{CNOT}(q_a, q_1)} |x\rangle_{q_0} |x \oplus y\rangle_{q_1} |x\rangle_{q_a} \\ &\xrightarrow{\text{CNOT}(q_0, q_a)} |x\rangle_{q_0} |x \oplus y\rangle_{q_1} |x \oplus x\rangle_{q_a} = |x\rangle_{q_0} |x \oplus y\rangle_{q_1} |0\rangle_{q_a} \end{aligned}$$

The final state is $|\psi_{final}\rangle = |x, x \oplus y\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_a$. The ancilla is disentangled and restored to $|0\rangle_a$ for all basis inputs, satisfying the clean ancilla safety definition.

Subspace Invariance We examine the evolution of the linear subspace spanned by valid clean states. Let $\mathcal{V}_{clean} = \text{span}\{|q_0 q_1\rangle |0\rangle_a\}$ be the subspace where the ancilla is in $|0\rangle$. The basis vectors for this subspace are $\{|000\rangle, |010\rangle, |100\rangle, |110\rangle\}$.

1. Detailed Trace of a Representative Basis Vector Let us track the evolution of the basis vector $|100\rangle$ (where $q_0 = 1, q_1 = 0, q_a = 0$). This state is non-trivial because the control qubit q_0 is active.

– **Input State:**

$$|\psi_0\rangle = |1\rangle_{q_0} |0\rangle_{q_1} |0\rangle_{q_a} \in \mathcal{V}_{clean}$$

– **After Gate 1** ($q_0 \rightarrow q_a$): Since $q_0 = 1$, the ancilla flips to $|1\rangle$.

$$|\psi_1\rangle = |1\rangle_{q_0} |0\rangle_{q_1} |1\rangle_{q_a}$$

Observation: The state vector has left the subspace \mathcal{V}_{clean} . It is now in the orthogonal subspace \mathcal{V}_{dirty} (where $q_a = 1$).

– **After Gate 2** ($q_a \rightarrow q_1$): Since $q_a = 1$ (dirty), it activates the second gate, flipping q_1 .

$$|\psi_2\rangle = |1\rangle_{q_0} |1\rangle_{q_1} |1\rangle_{q_a}$$

Observation: The computation is performed correctly, but the state remains outside \mathcal{V}_{clean} .

– **After Gate 3** ($q_0 \rightarrow q_a$): Since $q_0 = 1$ still holds, the ancilla flips again ($1 \oplus 1 = 0$).

$$|\psi_{final}\rangle = |1\rangle_{q_0} |1\rangle_{q_1} |0\rangle_{q_a} \in \mathcal{V}_{clean}$$

Conclusion: The final vector returns to the clean subspace.

2. *Summary of Full Basis Evolution* Similarly, we can verify the evolution for the remaining basis vectors of \mathcal{V}_{clean} . The results are summarized below:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{U} |000\rangle &= |000\rangle \in \mathcal{V} & \hat{U} |010\rangle &= |010\rangle \in \mathcal{V} \\ \hat{U} |100\rangle &= |110\rangle \in \mathcal{V} & \hat{U} |110\rangle &= |100\rangle \in \mathcal{V}\end{aligned}$$

Geometric Conclusion Although the intermediate states (like $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$) may rotate out of \mathcal{V}_{clean} into the dirty subspace, the unitary U maps every basis vector of \mathcal{V}_{clean} back into \mathcal{V}_{clean} . Since the operator is linear, this implies:

$$U(\mathcal{V}_{clean}) = \mathcal{V}_{clean}$$

Thus, the clean ancilla safety is geometrically satisfied.

Commutativity of Reflector Finally, we apply our reduction theorem by verifying the commutativity of the unitary U with the Householder reflection operator $Q_{\mathcal{V}}$. For the clean subspace determined by $|0\rangle_a$, the reflection operator is derived as:

$$Q_{\mathcal{V}} = 2(I_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0|_a) - I_{W \cup A} = I_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes Z_a.$$

We verify $[U, Q_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0$ by checking if the operator $Q_{\mathcal{V}}$ remains invariant under the conjugation of each gate in the sequence $U = U_3 U_2 U_1$. We denote the evolving operator as $Q^{(t)}$.

Initialization: $Q^{(0)} = I_{q_0} \otimes I_{q_1} \otimes Z_{q_a}$.

Step 1: $U_1 = \text{CNOT}(q_0, q_a)$. Using the propagation rule $\text{CNOT}_{c,t}(I_c \otimes Z_t) \text{CNOT}_{c,t} = Z_c \otimes Z_t$:

$$Q^{(1)} = U_1 Q^{(0)} U_1^\dagger = Z_{q_0} \otimes I_{q_1} \otimes Z_{q_a}.$$

Step 2: $U_2 = \text{CNOT}(q_a, q_1)$. Here q_a is the control qubit. Since the control qubit's Z-operator commutes with CNOT ($\text{CNOT}_{c,t} Z_c = Z_c \text{CNOT}_{c,t}$):

$$Q^{(2)} = U_2 Q^{(1)} U_2^\dagger = Z_{q_0} \otimes I_{q_1} \otimes Z_{q_a}.$$

Step 3: $U_3 = \text{CNOT}(q_0, q_a)$. We apply the conjugation to $Z_{q_0} \otimes Z_{q_a}$. Note that $\text{CNOT}_{c,t}$ maps $Z_c \otimes Z_t$ to $I_c \otimes Z_t$:

$$Q^{(3)} = U_3 Q^{(2)} U_3^\dagger = I_{q_0} \otimes I_{q_1} \otimes Z_{q_a}.$$

Conclusion: Since $Q^{(3)} = Q^{(0)} = I_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes Z_a$, we have $U Q_{\mathcal{V}} U^\dagger = Q_{\mathcal{V}}$, which implies $[U, Q_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0$. By Theorem 1, the circuit is clean safe.

A.1 Motivating Example: Bridge based GHZ Preparation

To demonstrate the capabilities of our verification tool, we introduce a parameterized family of GHZ state preparation circuits designed for architectures with limited connectivity.

The Bridge Gate Concept In Superconducting Quantum Processors (SQPs), qubit connectivity is typically restricted to a sparse coupling map (e.g., nearest-neighbor). Executing a CNOT between non-adjacent qubits usually requires inserting a chain of SWAP gates, which incurs high overhead (3 CNOTs per SWAP). To mitigate this, Itoko et al. [12] proposed the *Bridge Gate* technique. Instead of swapping states, a bridge gate utilizes an intermediate qubit (ancilla) to mediate the interaction. As shown in Fig. 4, a logical CNOT between control q_c and target q_t is realized via an ancilla a .

Benchmark Design: Cascaded GHZ Generation We construct an n -qubit GHZ state ($|0\dots 0\rangle + |1\dots 1\rangle$) by cascading $n - 1$ bridge gates. Each step performs a logical CNOT from q_i to q_{i+1} via an ancilla. To evaluate robustness and resource efficiency, we define four variants of this benchmark based on two dimensions: *Safety Property* and *Ancilla Allocation*.

1. *Safety Property (Clean vs. Dirty)*. This dimension defines the assumption on the initial state of the ancilla and the gate construction used:

- **Clean Bridge (3-CNOTs)**: As Fig 4 shows, this circuit assumes the ancilla starts in the ground state $|0\rangle$. The sequence is $CX(q_c, a) \rightarrow CX(a, q_t) \rightarrow CX(q_c, a)$. *Verification Challenge*: If the ancilla is initialized to $|0\rangle$, it returns to $|0\rangle$ and performs the correct logic. However, if the ancilla is dirty (e.g., $|1\rangle$), the target qubit suffers a bit-flip error. This requires verifying *Clean Safety*.
- **Dirty Bridge (4-CNOTs)**: As Fig 5 shows, this circuit makes no assumption on the ancilla’s initial state. It appends a fourth gate, $CX(a, q_t)$, to the Clean Bridge sequence. *Verification Challenge*: This construction guarantees that the ancilla is restored and the logical CNOT is correct regardless of the ancilla’s initial state (even if entangled). This requires verifying *Dirty Safety*.

Fig. 4: A Bridge CNOT circuit implementing a mediated operation. The ancilla q_a is used to transfer information and is uncomputed at the end to satisfy dirty safety.

Fig. 5: A Bridge CNOT circuit implemented by a dirty ancilla between q_0 and q_1 . The ancilla q_a is used to transfer information and is uncomputed at the end to satisfy dirty safety.

2. *Ancilla Allocation (Distinct vs. Shared)*. This dimension defines how ancilla resources are managed across the cascade:

- **Distinct Ancillae (Linear)**: Each logical CNOT uses a fresh, dedicated ancilla. For an n -qubit GHZ state, this requires $n - 1$ ancilla qubits. This represents a resource-rich scenario where spatial locality is prioritized. The example circuit is shown in Fig 6.
- **Shared Ancilla (Reused)**: A single ancilla is reused sequentially for all $n - 1$ logical operations. This represents a resource-constrained scenario. *Verification Challenge*: This introduces complex temporal dependencies. A failure to restore the ancilla in step i will propagate errors to all subsequent steps $j > i$, making verification significantly harder. The example circuit is shown in Fig 7.

Fig. 6: A cascaded GHZ quantum circuit design utilizing two dirty ancilla qubits (a_0, a_1) to mediate interactions between data qubits.

These variants provide a comprehensive suite for benchmarking quantum verification tools, ranging from simple clean checks to complex, interference-prone dirty safety verification.

Fig. 7: A cascaded GHZ quantum circuit design utilizing one dirty ancilla qubits a_0 to mediate interactions between data qubits.

B Proof

Proof of Lemma 1. Let $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes \text{span}\{|0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}\}$.

(\Rightarrow) Assume U is clean-safe on \mathcal{A} . By definition, for any $|\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \in \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}}$,

$$U(|\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}) = |\psi'\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}} \in \mathcal{V}.$$

By linearity, for any $|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$, $U|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$. Thus,

$$U(\mathcal{V}) \subseteq \mathcal{V}.$$

Since U is unitary, it is an isometry and preserves subspace dimensions:

$$\dim(U(\mathcal{V})) = \dim(\mathcal{V}).$$

For finite-dimensional subspaces, inclusion ($U(\mathcal{V}) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$) and dimension equality imply equality:

$$U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V}.$$

(\Leftarrow) Assume $U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V}$. For any $|\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \in \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}}$, let $|\phi\rangle = |\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}$. Clearly $|\phi\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$. The assumption implies $U|\phi\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$. By the definition of \mathcal{V} , any vector in \mathcal{V} takes the form $|\xi\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}$. Hence, there exists $|\psi'\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \in \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}}$ such that

$$U(|\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}) = |\psi'\rangle_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}},$$

which satisfies the definition of clean safety. \square

Proof of Lemma 2. Recall that $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes \text{span}\{|0\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}\}$. Let $P_{\mathcal{V}} = I_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0|_{\mathcal{A}}$ be the orthogonal projector onto \mathcal{V} . The operator $Q_{\mathcal{V}}$ is defined as:

$$Q_{\mathcal{V}} = 2P_{\mathcal{V}} - I.$$

Since the identity operator I commutes with any operator, the commutator relation simplifies to:

$$[U, Q_{\mathcal{V}}] = [U, 2P_{\mathcal{V}} - I] = 2[U, P_{\mathcal{V}}].$$

Thus, $[U, Q_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0 \iff [U, P_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0$. The proof reduces to showing $U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V} \iff [U, P_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0$.

(\Rightarrow) Assume $U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V}$. Consider the operator $R = UP_{\mathcal{V}}U^\dagger$. Since U is unitary, R is an orthogonal projector. For any $|u\rangle \in \mathcal{H}$, let $|v\rangle = P_{\mathcal{V}}(U^\dagger|u\rangle)$. By definition, $|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$. Then,

$$R|u\rangle = U|v\rangle \in U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V}.$$

Thus $\text{Im}(R) = \mathcal{V}$. Since the orthogonal projector onto a subspace is unique,

$$UP_{\mathcal{V}}U^\dagger = P_{\mathcal{V}}.$$

Right-multiplying by U yields $UP_{\mathcal{V}} = P_{\mathcal{V}}U$, i.e., $[U, P_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0$.

(\Leftarrow) Assume $[U, P_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0$. For any $|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$, we have $P_{\mathcal{V}}|v\rangle = |v\rangle$. Applying the projection to the transformed vector $U|v\rangle$:

$$P_{\mathcal{V}}(U|v\rangle) = U(P_{\mathcal{V}}|v\rangle) = U|v\rangle.$$

Since $P_{\mathcal{V}}$ acts as the identity only on \mathcal{V} , this implies $U|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}$. Thus, $U(\mathcal{V}) \subseteq \mathcal{V}$. Since U is an isometry on a finite-dimensional space, inclusion implies equality:

$$U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V}. \quad \square$$

Proof of Lemma 3. (\Rightarrow) Assume U is dirty safe with respect to the full ancilla register $\mathcal{A} = \{a_1, \dots, a_m\}$. By definition, there exists a unitary V on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}}$ such that $U = V \otimes I_{\mathcal{A}}$, which can be expanded as:

$$U = V \otimes I_{a_1} \otimes \dots \otimes I_{a_m}.$$

Then, for any $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, any state $|\varphi\rangle_{a_j} \in \mathcal{H}_{a_j}$, and any state $|\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W} \cup (\mathcal{A} \setminus \{a_j\})} \in \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W} \cup (\mathcal{A} \setminus \{a_j\})}$, we have

$$U(|\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W} \cup (\mathcal{A} \setminus \{a_j\})} \otimes |\varphi\rangle_{a_j}) = (V \otimes I_{\mathcal{A} \setminus \{a_j\}}) |\psi\rangle_{\mathcal{W} \cup (\mathcal{A} \setminus \{a_j\})} \otimes |\varphi\rangle_{a_j},$$

which shows U is dirty safe with respect to a_j alone.

(\Leftarrow) Assume for every $a_j \in \mathcal{A}$, U is dirty safe on a_j . That is,

$$\forall j \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \exists V_j \text{ on } \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W} \cup (\mathcal{A} \setminus \{a_j\})},$$

such that

$$U = V_j \otimes I_{a_j}.$$

Since this holds for all $j = 1, \dots, m$, U acts as the identity on every ancilla qubit independently. Hence, U acts as the identity on the entire ancilla register \mathcal{A} :

$$U = V \otimes I_{\mathcal{A}}$$

for some unitary V on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}}$. □

Proof of Theorem 1. This result follows directly from the chain of equivalences established in Lemma 1 and Lemma 2.

First, by Lemma 1, clean safety is equivalent to the invariance of the clean subspace \mathcal{V} :

$$U \text{ is clean-safe on } \mathcal{A} \iff U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V}.$$

Second, by Lemma 2, the invariance of subspace \mathcal{V} is equivalent to the commutation of U with the operator $Q_{\mathcal{V}}$:

$$U(\mathcal{V}) = \mathcal{V} \iff [U, Q_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0.$$

Combining these two equivalences yields:

$$U \text{ is clean-safe on } \mathcal{A} \iff [U, Q_{\mathcal{V}}] = 0. \quad \square$$

Proof of Theorem 2. Let $\mathcal{V}_{\varphi} = \mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes \text{span}\{|\varphi\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}\}$ and $P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}} = I_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes |\varphi\rangle\langle\varphi|_{\mathcal{A}}$. The proof proceeds by establishing a chain of equivalences.

1. Clean safety \iff Subspace invariance

- By Definition, U is clean-safe for $|\varphi\rangle_{\mathcal{A}}$ implies that for all $|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}_{\varphi}$, $U|v\rangle \in \mathcal{V}_{\varphi}$. Thus, $U(\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}) \subseteq \mathcal{V}_{\varphi}$.
- Since U is unitary (isometry) and $\dim(\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}) < \infty$:

$$U(\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}) \subseteq \mathcal{V}_{\varphi} \implies U(\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}) = \mathcal{V}_{\varphi}.$$

2. Subspace invariance \iff Commutativity

- Assume $U(\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}) = \mathcal{V}_{\varphi}$. Then the projection onto the subspace is invariant under conjugation by U :

$$UP_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}}U^{\dagger} = P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}} \iff UP_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}} = P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}}U \iff [U, P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}}] = 0.$$

- Since $Q_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}} = 2P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}} - I$, and $[U, I] = 0$:

$$[U, P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}}] = 0 \iff [U, 2P_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}} - I] = 0 \iff [U, Q_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}}] = 0.$$

Combining **1** and **2**, we conclude:

$$U \text{ is clean-safe for } |\varphi\rangle_{\mathcal{A}} \iff [U, Q_{\mathcal{V}_{\varphi}}] = 0. \quad \square$$

Proof of Theorem 3. (\implies) Assume U is dirty-safe on \mathcal{A} . By Lemma 3, U acts as the identity on the ancilla register \mathcal{A} (up to a unitary on \mathcal{W}). That is, $U = V_{\mathcal{W}} \otimes I_{\mathcal{A}}$. Since the identity operator $I_{\mathcal{A}}$ commutes with any operator on $\mathcal{H}_{\mathcal{A}}$, U commutes with $Q_{(a_i, \varphi)}$ for any a_i and any φ .

(\impliedby) Assume the commutativity condition holds:

$$\forall a_i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall |\varphi\rangle \in \{|\varphi_1\rangle, |\varphi_2\rangle\} : [U, Q_{(a_i, |\varphi\rangle)}] = 0.$$

By Lemma 3, it suffices to prove that U acts as the identity on each individual ancilla qubit a_i (i.e., U is dirty-safe on each a_i).

Fix an arbitrary ancilla qubit a_i . By Theorem 2, the commutativity conditions imply that U is clean-safe for both $|\varphi_1\rangle_{a_i}$ and $|\varphi_2\rangle_{a_i}$. Let us decompose the action of U relative to the basis aligned with $|\varphi_1\rangle$. Without loss of generality, identify $|\varphi_1\rangle$ with the basis state $|0\rangle$ and let $|0\rangle^\perp = |1\rangle$. Since U is clean-safe for $|0\rangle$, it must be block-diagonal with respect to this basis:

$$U = V_0 \otimes |0\rangle\langle 0|_{a_i} + V_1 \otimes |1\rangle\langle 1|_{a_i},$$

where V_0, V_1 are unitaries on the remaining qubits.

Now consider the second state $|\varphi_2\rangle$. Since $0 < |\langle \varphi_1 | \varphi_2 \rangle| < 1$, we can write $|\varphi_2\rangle = \alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle$ with non-zero coefficients $\alpha, \beta \in \mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$. Applying U to an arbitrary state $|\psi\rangle$ on the working register tensored with $|\varphi_2\rangle$:

$$U(|\psi\rangle \otimes |\varphi_2\rangle) = \alpha(V_0 |\psi\rangle) \otimes |0\rangle + \beta(V_1 |\psi\rangle) \otimes |1\rangle.$$

Since U is also clean-safe for $|\varphi_2\rangle$, the output must separate as $|\psi'\rangle \otimes |\varphi_2\rangle = |\psi'\rangle \otimes (\alpha |0\rangle + \beta |1\rangle)$. Matching the coefficients for $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ implies:

$$V_0 |\psi\rangle = |\psi'\rangle \quad \text{and} \quad V_1 |\psi\rangle = |\psi'\rangle.$$

Thus $V_0 = V_1$. Consequently, $U = V_0 \otimes (|0\rangle\langle 0| + |1\rangle\langle 1|) = V_0 \otimes I_{a_i}$. This proves that U acts trivially on the ancilla qubit a_i . Since this holds for all $a_i \in A$, U is dirty-safe on A . \square

C Implementation Details of Repair Components

C.1 Entanglement Check via Partial Trace

To efficiently verify this, we reduce the problem to a purity computation defined by a partial trace followed by a trace calculation. Specifically, we calculate the reduced operator $O_{a,\varphi} = \text{Tr}_{\mathcal{W} \cup \mathcal{A} / \{a\}}(Q_{(a,|\varphi\rangle)})$ and check if $\text{Tr}(O_{a,\varphi}^2) = 1$ for $\varphi \in \{0, +\}$. A result of $\text{Tr}(O_{a,\varphi}^2) < 1$ for any $\varphi \in \{0, +\}$, indicates that the circuit causes entanglement between the ancilla a and other qubit, otherwise the error is separable with $\text{Tr}(O_{a,\varphi}^2) = 1$.

C.2 Angle Calculation

Recall $Q_{(a,|0\rangle)} = I_{\mathcal{W} \cup \mathcal{A} / \{a\}} \otimes Z$ and $Q_{(a,|+\rangle)} = I_{\mathcal{W} \cup \mathcal{A} / \{a\}} \otimes X$. $Q'_{(a,|0\rangle)} = U Q_{(a,|0\rangle)} U^\dagger$ and $Q'_{(a,|+\rangle)} = U Q_{(a,|+\rangle)} U^\dagger$. Since the error is separable, Then there exists $O_{a,0}$ and $O_{a,+}$ that are both unitary, satisfying

$$Q'_{(a,|0\rangle)} = I_{\mathcal{W} \cup \mathcal{A} / \{a\}} \otimes O_{a,0}$$

and

$$Q'_{(a,|+\rangle)} = I_{\mathcal{W} \cup \mathcal{A} / \{a\}} \otimes O_{a,+}.$$

Both error occurs If `LogicError` and `PhaseError` both occur, then we find $\theta_{z1}, \theta_x, \theta_{z2}$ which satisfy:

$$R_Z(\theta_{z1})R_X(\theta_x)R_Z(\theta_{z2}) \cdot O_{a,0} \cdot R_Z(\theta_{z1})R_X(\theta_x)R_Z(\theta_{z2})^\dagger = Z$$

and:

$$R_Z(\theta_{z1})R_X(\theta_x)R_Z(\theta_{z2}) \cdot O_{a,+} \cdot R_Z(\theta_{z1})R_X(\theta_x)R_Z(\theta_{z2})^\dagger = X.$$

Existence and Uniqueness of the Solution. The problem of finding the repair angles $(\theta_{z1}, \theta_x, \theta_{z2})$ is equivalent to constructing the inverse unitary U_{err}^\dagger such that the corrected state aligns with the computational basis. **Existence** is guaranteed by the Euler decomposition theorem, which states that any element of the special unitary group $SU(2)$ can be parameterized by three real rotations $R_Z(\gamma)R_X(\beta)R_Z(\alpha)$. Since the accumulated error U_{err} is a single-qubit unitary operator, there strictly exists a set of angles that satisfies the alignment constraints for both the $|0\rangle$ and $|+\rangle$ states simultaneously.

Regarding **Uniqueness**, the standard Euler decomposition is generally unique up to coordinate singularities (Gimbal lock) and periodicities. However, we enforce a strict unique solution within the principal interval $(-\pi, \pi]$ through our constructive algorithm. First, the periodicity ambiguity is resolved by the use of the two-argument arctangent function (`arctan2`), which maps all inputs deterministically to the principal range. Second, the potential degeneracy at the poles (where $\theta_x = 0$ or π , causing θ_{z1} and θ_{z2} to become linearly dependent) is resolved by the sequential nature of our derivation. Specifically, θ_{z1} is uniquely determined by the projection of the Z -vector onto the Y - Z plane; once fixed, θ_x and θ_{z2} are subsequently determined by the remaining deviations. Thus, for any physically valid error unitary, our analytic procedure yields exactly one repair sequence.

LogicError only or PhaseError only When `LogicError` is detected only, then we find $\theta \in (-\pi, \pi]$ satisfying:

$$R_X(\theta)O_{a,0}R_X(\theta)^\dagger = Z.$$

When `PhaseError` is detected only, then we find $\theta \in (-\pi, \pi]$ satisfying:

$$R_Z(\theta)O_{a,+}R_Z(\theta)^\dagger = X.$$

The existence and uniqueness of the solution θ are guaranteed by the algebraic constraints imposed by the diagnosis phase. For a pure `LogicError`, the commutativity check $[U_{\text{err}}, X] = 0$ restricts the error unitary to the subgroup generated by the Pauli- X operator. Geometrically, this confines the Bloch vector of the ancilla to the Y - Z plane. Consequently, the optimization problem reduces to finding a unique rotation angle on a unit circle that aligns the vector with the north pole $|0\rangle$, which is analytically solvable via $\theta = \arctan 2(r_y, r_z)$. Similarly, a pure `PhaseError` implies $[U_{\text{err}}, Z] = 0$, constraining the state to the equatorial

X - Y plane. The solution is thus the unique azimuthal angle required to restore the $|+\rangle$ state, derived as $\theta = \arctan 2(-r_y, r_x)$. In both cases, the dimensionality reduction from the full Bloch sphere to a single great circle ensures a one-to-one mapping between the error syndrome and the repair angle within the principal branch.

D More Experiment Results about Soundness and Scalability of Verification

Table 3 shows more detail comparing performance of different backends.

Table 3: **Comparison of verification efficiency and results.** Time is in seconds. “—” indicates the step is skipped due to timeout/memout.

Benchmark	N	Depth	Matrix		Quokka-Sharp		QCEC	
			Time	Output	Time	Output	Time	Output
Grover _F	7	55	0.1	True	6.2	True	0.2	True
	9	99	1.0	True	Timeout	—	0.3	True
	11	195	38.3	True	Timeout	—	0.3	True
	19	1603	Memout	—	Timeout	—	0.4	True
	29	14771	Memout	—	Timeout	—	1.9	True
	35	51459	Memout	—	Timeout	—	8.0	True
	39	115779	Memout	—	Timeout	—	25.9	True
Grover _{r-1}	99	387	Memout	—	7.0	True	1.0	True
	179	707	Memout	—	21.8	True	2.0	True
	239	947	Memout	—	41.9	True	3.1	True
	319	1267	Memout	—	68.3	True	5.4	True
	399	1587	Memout	—	112.2	True	6.6	True
	479	1907	Memout	—	162.4	True	8.6	True
	559	2227	Memout	—	223.8	True	13.3	True
699	2787	Memout	—	370.0	True	19.5	True	
MCX	199	392	Memout	—	0.6	True	2.2	True
	599	1192	Memout	—	3.7	True	8.7	True
	999	1992	Memout	—	10.0	True	18.7	True
	1399	2792	Memout	—	19.2	True	35.3	True
	1599	3192	Memout	—	25.9	True	44.8	True
	1799	3592	Memout	—	31.8	True	57.7	True
	1999	3992	Memout	—	38.9	True	63.1	True
	3999	7992	Memout	—	174.0	True	514.4	True
	5999	11992	Memout	—	414.4	True	Memout	—
	7999	15992	Memout	—	634.4	True	Memout	—
9999	19992	Memout	—	1115.6	True	Memout	—	
Adder	13	44	159.5	True	0.1	True	0.7	True
	599	2388	Memout	—	3.3	True	13.3	True
	999	3988	Memout	—	8.8	True	38.9	True
	1499	5988	Memout	—	19.3	True	93.4	True
	1999	7988	Memout	—	33.1	True	139.3	True
	2999	11988	Memout	—	71.1	True	444.8	True
	3999	15988	Memout	—	141.9	True	1025.3	True
	4999	19988	Memout	—	218.9	True	Memout	—
	5999	23988	Memout	—	317.8	True	Memout	—
Bridge GHZ	1399	2797	Memout	—	2.4	True	27.3	True
	1799	3597	Memout	—	4.5	True	40.8	True
	1999	3997	Memout	—	5.4	True	48.3	True
	2399	4797	Memout	—	7.6	True	74.9	True
	3599	7197	Memout	—	8.0	True	234.2	True
	4399	8797	Memout	—	10.4	True	Memout	—
	4799	9597	Memout	—	11.0	True	Memout	—
Reqomp-MCX	11	9	2.8	PhaseError	0.1	PhaseError	0.3	PhaseError
	13	11	92.4	PhaseError	0.1	PhaseError	0.3	PhaseError
	15	13	Memout	—	0.1	PhaseError	0.3	PhaseError
Identity Random	5	47	0.1	True	0.4	True	0.2	True
	6	53	0.1	True	1.4	True	0.2	True
	7	54	0.2	True	5.1	True	0.2	True
Random Circuit	30	11	Memout	—	0.1	BothError	0.3	BothError
	50	14	Memout	—	0.1	BothError	0.4	BothError
	70	4	Memout	—	0.1	BothError	0.5	BothError